

ARDC Survey on Cloud Services Usage in Research

Final Report

Dr Andrew Treloar, Director International Strategy

Dr Emma Crott, Chief of Staff

Updated with *corrigenda* 03/08/2023

Cover Image - Siarhei - 337007459 / adobestock.com

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8213503

Suggested citation:

ARDC Ltd. ARDC Survey on Cloud Services Usage in Research. 2023. Available from doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8213503

Viewed online at:

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8213503>

Published:

3 August 2023

Acknowledgement of Country

We acknowledge the traditional custodians throughout Australia and their continuing connection to, and deep knowledge of, the land and waters. We pay our respects to Elders both past and present.

CONTENTS

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
2. BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT	4
3. DISCIPLINE GROUPING	5
4. RESPONDENTS	6
5. GENERAL USE OF CLOUD	8
6. COMMERCIAL CLOUD	11
7. ARDC NECTAR RESEARCH CLOUD	18
8. NECTAR CLOUD vs. COMMERCIAL CLOUD	22
9. AUSTRALIAN RESULTS VS CANADIAN RESULTS	23
9.1 Background	23
9.2 Respondents	23
9.3 General Use of Cloud	23
9.4 Commercial Cloud	24
9.5 Nectar Research Cloud/Alliance Community Cloud	24
10. CONCLUSIONS	25
APPENDIX A: SURVEY DETAILS	26
A.1 Response rate	26
A.2 Survey issues	26

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The ARDC has operated the Nectar Research Cloud since 2012 to provide Australia's research community with fast, interactive, self-service access to large-scale computing infrastructure, software and data. There are also now other providers in the market: clouds associated with NCI and Pawsey, and commercial clouds from Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft and Google, among others.

In order to get a better understanding of how researchers in Australia are using cloud resources, the ARDC ran a survey of research cloud users in June 2023.

The key findings from an analysis of the survey results are:

- Researchers across all Field of Research (FoR) codes use cloud technologies, but Biological Sciences, Earth Sciences, Health Sciences and Information and Computer Sciences dominated in this survey.
- Over half of respondents were using cloud technologies of all kinds to store or process controlled or sensitive data.
- The two most significant factors driving the choice of cloud platform were ease of use and cost.
- Over half of respondents acknowledged using a commercial cloud provider (e.g. AWS, Azure, Google Compute Platform, Oracle Cloud), with the budget for this coming from a mix of institutional funds and research grants, as well as industry grants, personal funding and cloud research credits.
- Almost two thirds of respondents had used the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud.
- Across a wide range of institutional, national and some international cloud providers, the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud was both used the most and received the highest rating for importance in supporting the respondent's research.
- The overwhelming majority of respondents were happy with the available range of platforms or software services available on the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud.

2. BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT

Cloud computing has emerged as a transformative technology for the research sector, offering numerous advantages that have revolutionised the way research is conducted and accelerated scientific progress. This innovative paradigm for access to compute power provides on-demand access to a vast pool of computing resources, enabling researchers to store, process, and analyse large volumes of data more efficiently than ever before.

One key benefit of cloud computing for the research sector is the scalability it offers. Researchers often deal with massive datasets that require significant computational power. Cloud platforms allow for easy scaling up or down of computing resources, ensuring that researchers have access to the necessary processing power and storage capacity whenever they need it. This scalability eliminates the need for investing in expensive hardware infrastructure, making it cost-effective for research institutions of all sizes.

Additionally, cloud computing enables collaboration and data sharing among researchers across different locations. By storing data and research tools on the cloud, multiple researchers can access and work on the same resources simultaneously, fostering collaboration and enhancing productivity.

The ARDC has operated the Nectar Research Cloud since 2012 to provide Australia's research community with fast, interactive, self-service access to large-scale computing infrastructure, software and data. There are also now other providers in the market: clouds associated with NCI and Pawsey, and commercial clouds from Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft and Google, among others.

In order to get a better understanding of how researchers in Australia are using cloud resources, the ARDC ran a survey in June 2023. This survey was based on one conducted by the Digital Research Alliance of Canada, which was intended to provide a first insight for future efforts related to cloud technologies in Canadian research. The ARDC gratefully acknowledges their permission to take their survey questions and adapt and extend them for an Australian setting.

More information about the Canadian survey and a report of their findings can be found at <https://alliancecan.ca/en/latest/news/new-report-cloud-services-research>.

More information about the ARDC survey can be found at <https://ardc.edu.au/article/ardc-survey-on-cloud-services-usage-in-research/>.

3. DISCIPLINE GROUPING

The Digital Research Alliance of Canada survey results were grouped for analysis based on the Canadian Research and Development Classification (CRDC) 2020. For simplicity, they classified researchers into three large groups: Sciences and Engineering (SE), which includes Natural Sciences, Engineering and Technology, and Agriculture and Veterinary Sciences; Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), which includes Humanities and the Arts, and Social Sciences; and Health Research (HR), which includes Medical, Health and Life Sciences.

The ARDC Survey on Cloud Services Usage in Research (Australian Survey) asked respondents to identify themselves against multiple research domains using the Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification (ANZSRC) Field of Research (FoR) codes. To simplify comparison with the Canadian survey, the same three groupings were used, with the following FoR code assignments being made (relevant 2 digit code in parentheses):

- SE: Agriculture Veterinary and Food Sciences (30), Built Environment and Design (33), Chemical Sciences (34), Earth Sciences (37), Engineering (40), Environmental Sciences (41), Information and Computer Sciences (46), Mathematical Sciences (49), Physical Sciences (51)
- SSH: Commerce Management Tourism and Services (35), Creative Arts and Writing (36), Economics (38), Education (39), History Heritage and Archaeology (43), Human Society (44), Indigenous Studies (45), Language Communication and Culture (47), Law and Legal Studies (48), Philosophy and Religious Studies (50), Psychology (52)
- HR: Biological Sciences (31), Biomedical and Clinical Sciences (32), Health Sciences (42)

Many respondents selected multiple domains. Of the 173 total responses, 109 selected an FoR code in the SE domain, 56 selected an FoR code in the SSH domain, and 79 selected an FoR code in the HR domain.

This report will discuss the overall survey results, but also mention differences between the three high-level groupings when these appear significant.

4. RESPONDENTS

Respondents to the survey covered a range of sector roles:

and most states and territories:

When considering the discipline distribution, all FoR codes were represented, but Biological Sciences, Information and Computer Sciences, and Health Science were the three most represented:

In terms of the Canadian higher-level groupings, nearly half of the respondents selected at least one FOR code in the Science and Engineering (SE) grouping (as more than one code could be selected, the numbers sum to more than the total number of responses received):

FOR Codes by high-level groups
(no. of respondents)

5. GENERAL USE OF CLOUD

The overwhelming majority of respondents (97.26%) are current or past users of cloud resources. Across a wide range of institutional, national and some international cloud providers, the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud was both the most used compute cloud (140 out of 173 responses) and received the highest rating for importance in supporting the respondent’s research.

Cloud services were used for a wide range of purposes, including storage and a range of computing specific purposes, across all FoR codes. Notable was the use of cloud for high-performance computing capabilities (56.16%), accessing eResearch platforms (36.3%) many of which are deployed on Nectar, and analysis (41.1%). Software as a Service (SaaS), Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), and Platform as a Service (PaaS) all ranked much lower. When considering differences between high-level discipline groupings, the Health Research (HR) and Science and Engineering (SE) groupings were broadly comparable, while researchers who selected one of the Social Science and Humanities (SSH) codes were less likely to use Object Storage and HPC capabilities.

How cloud services were accessed was quite variable, with many respondents using multiple methods. A direct terminal connection via something like Secure Shell (73.97%), and using a software intermediation layer (76.71%) were the most common, with access through a web browser (67.81%) a close third. Interestingly, nearly a quarter of respondents (24.66%) accessed cloud resources through an eResearch Platform such as Galaxy, EcoCommons or the Characterisation Virtual Laboratory, all of which have received significant ARDC co-investment.

The two most significant factors driving the choice of cloud platform for all respondents were ease of use (82.19%) and cost (73.97%):

There were some interesting differences between factors when comparing the discipline groupings. Respondents included in the SSH grouping were **less** likely to be influenced by ease of use or cost, and more likely than HR or SE to be influenced by other factors (such as institutional requirements or support).

Factor	HR %	SE %	SSH %
Ease of use	84.51%	81.52%	79.59%

Cost	76.06%	71.74%	69.39%
Scalability	46.48%	41.30%	30.61%
Vendor-agnostic features	21.13%	33.70%	16.33%
Cloud-specific services and features	29.58%	33.70%	26.53%
Other (please specify)	26.76%	27.17%	34.69%

There were also significant differences by discipline grouping in the proportions of respondents who were using cloud technologies of all kinds to store or process controlled or sensitive data (e.g., Indigenous data, personal data, data subject to a data sharing agreement or specific security requirements), with this being significantly more prevalent with HR and SSH respondents than with those in the SE grouping.

6. COMMERCIAL CLOUD

Over 55% of respondents acknowledged using a commercial cloud provider (e.g. AWS, Azure, Google Compute Platform, Oracle Cloud):

The budget for this came from a mix of institutional funds, research grants (these first two sources were the largest), as well as industry grants, personal funding and cloud research credits:

The amounts of cloud credits consumed/spent across all respondents were more than the amounts of research funds at the low-end but this pattern was reversed for the bands \$5K to \$50K, and \$50K to \$100K:

When it came to expenditure on cloud computing (both cloud credits and research funds), half of Science and Engineering (SE) respondents (46.78%) reported using such funds on commercial cloud resources, compared to 43% for Health Research (HR) respondents and 41% for Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) respondents. Respondents in the HR and SE groups were the only ones to report in the \$100K or more band for cloud/in-kind credits (but only one respondent in each group). None of the SSH respondents reported using more than \$5K in cloud/in-kind credits.

Removing “not sure” and \$0 responses resulted in the following figures for cloud/in-kind credits:

- HR - 21.5% of respondents
- SE - 26.6% of respondents
- SSH - 21.4% of respondents

and the following figures for research or other funds:

- HR - 24.89% of respondents
- SE - 38.89% of respondents
- SSH - 17.875% of respondents

That is a significant extra draw on research or other funds for SE respondents, spread across all but the most expensive cost band:

For SSH respondents, the costs were not just expended by fewer of them, they were also skewed towards the lower cost bands:

No particular reason dominated when respondents were asked about their primary reasons for using a commercial cloud:

There was also considerable variety in the components of commercial cloud that were used, although virtual machines predominated in all three discipline groupings (of note here, cloud-specific software components were not a major driver, being listed by only 29.41% of respondents):

The use of commercial cloud for storing and sharing research outputs was also variable, with no single function dominating. Usage patterns were broadly comparable across all three discipline groups.

While there has been considerable discussion in the sector about issues relating to sensitive data, 30.51% of all respondents said that any of the content they stored or shared on the commercial cloud was controlled, high risk or sensitive. The fact that this number was as high as this may well reflect the impact of the vendors of commercial services establishing Australian data centres to avoid trans-border data flows. However, the discipline differences were striking. Nearly half (43.48%) of the SSH respondents indicated that any of their content fell into this category, as compared to 28% for SE, and 26.47% for HR. Given the bias of HR research towards areas that involve sensitive data, this suggests strongly that they are managing their data elsewhere. A somewhat higher percentage (39.71%) said that they had a need to securely share data stored on the commercial cloud with specific collaborators. Once again, SE and HR respondents answered in the affirmative (43.14% and 44.12% respectively), with SSH respondents noticeably lower (39.13%).

The difference between these two measures (actual content stored and need to share) suggests that not all respondents are yet comfortable with such sharing, despite having a need. There were also some significant differences between discipline groupings when looking at the means they used to transfer data stored on commercial cloud.

HR users preferred manual data transfer using Secure Shell or Secure File Transfer Protocol, followed by manually using software, and automatically using cloud tools:

SE users showed a similar usage pattern:

But SSH users favoured Secure Shell or Secure File Transfer Protocol and automatically using cloud tools, with manually using software a distant third:

Overall, half of the respondents (50%) said they had concerns about storing data on the commercial cloud (i.e., safety/security, sovereignty, backups, costs of hosting, downloading or moving data). When considering whether respondents had lost access to data stored on the commercial cloud due to lack of continuity of funding for their research, the percentage answering yes was 8.82% for HR researchers, 12% for SE, and 22.73% for SSH. This latter number is a cause for concern if the usage of commercial cloud increases and deserves further investigation.

Respondents were also asked if they would like support from the ARDC when using the commercial cloud. Less than a third (28.33%) answered yes, two fifths (40%) answered no, and just under a third (31.67%) were unsure. Answers were broadly comparable across discipline groupings. Some ambiguity about what sort of support was intended may have contributed to this result, and the issue of how best to support usage of commercial cloud requires further exploration and consideration.

7. ARDC NECTAR RESEARCH CLOUD

Almost two thirds of respondents (63.77%) had used the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud, with less than 10% being unsure. Science and Engineering (SE) respondents were the most prevalent user group (75.29%), followed by Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) (70.45%) and Health Research (HR) respondents (60.61%).

When asked about their primary reasons for using the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud, the answers varied, but two reasons were listed by almost half of all respondents - additional computational resources (51.9%) and cost (51.9%):

In general, the primary reasons varied little between discipline groups, with a couple of exceptions. Cost was listed as a driver by slightly more SSH respondents (53.85%) than SE (50.88%) or HR (50%) respondents. And replication was notably lower as a driver for HR (7.89%) than for SSH (11.54%) or SE (12.28%) respondents.

Of the various ARDC Nectar Research Cloud components used, the use of Virtual Machines predominated (44.3%), followed by Other (29.11%). As discussed in section A.2, a survey configuration error meant that this question was effectively answered as the primary reason (singular) for using the Nectar Research Cloud. Despite this, the focus on Virtual Machines still suggests a possible marketing/training opportunity around the benefits of alternative forms of access.

The overwhelming majority (78.48%) of respondents were happy with the available range of platforms and software services available on the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud and did not list any additional cloud services they wanted to see added. This number was slightly lower for HR users (71.05%) and SSH users (73.08%). When asked if there were particular platforms or software services they currently deployed or wished to deploy in their own cloud environments that they felt would be valuable to be offered as a national service for all researchers to access, the answers were similar: 73.42% overall said no, with HR (68.42%) and SSH users (63.38%) being more interested in possible wider deployment. Again, this suggests possible further work to identify what these platforms/services are, and to assess their redeployment potential.

A major focus of the survey was on the use of cloud technologies for sharing. Nearly half (49.36%) of the respondents had used the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud for sharing data with collaborators, or the public, with only small differences between discipline groupings. But when asked about storing data with no sharing involved, respondents in the SSH group were much less likely to answer yes (19.23%) than those in the HR (29.82%) or SE (29.95%) groupings. The SSH respondents had the highest percentage of Other sharing activity responses (30.77%) and it would be instructive to analyse these further as future work.

When asked whether the data they stored on the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud was controlled, high risk or sensitive, there were marked differences by discipline. Those who answered yes most strongly were the SSH group (23.08%), followed by HR (15.79%) and SE (10.53%). This was in contrast to the next question, which asked whether respondents needed to securely share data stored on the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud with specific collaborators. Here the SSH respondents answered yes the least (26.92%), followed by HR (31.58%) and SE (35.09%).

The majority (70.89%) of respondents overall had no concerns (safety, security, backups) about storing data on the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud.

The overwhelming majority of data transfer usage on the Nectar Research Cloud was manual, with the only real difference by discipline being that HR users did not select the ‘Automatically using software option’; but this was a low-scoring answer for SE and SSH as well:

There was a clear expressed need for tools to track cloud data storage and provide reminders to back up or migrate content, with 60.75% of respondents identifying this as a lack. However, over 20% of all respondents were not sure if such tools would be useful, which suggests an opportunity to provide information about the potential uses of such tool:

When asked about missing technical support methods, a wide range of options received small amounts of support. The most popular option was online community chat, which received 24.05% overall (around the same as those who indicated not sure). Demand for short video tutorials on basic cloud tasks from SSH users (19.23%) was double for HR users (10.53%), suggesting lower levels of technical comfort in the SSH community.

Respondents were also asked about which cloud-related training topics would be of interest to them. A large number of options were selected by a third or more of the respondents, but the two commercial options (commercial cloud usage, commercial cloud platforms) each received less than 10% support:

8. NECTAR CLOUD vs. COMMERCIAL CLOUD

When comparing respondents' use of the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud vs commercial cloud, there are a number of significant differences.

The reasons for using the different clouds varied, with access to additional computation resources and cost being the main reasons for use of the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud.

With respect to data transfer techniques, the respondents using the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud were much more likely to use a variety of manual methods, whereas a much larger proportion of respondents on commercial cloud also made use of cloud tools and automatic software methods. Again, this suggests a functionality or awareness gap that the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud could look to fill.

9. AUSTRALIAN RESULTS VS CANADIAN RESULTS

9.1 Background

While the ARDC Core Services team has run annual surveys, they have concentrated on the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud only. This survey was seen as an opportunity to expand the coverage to include commercial cloud, and benchmark the Australian experience against that of our Canadian colleagues.

9.2 Respondents

Nearly half of the respondents selected at least one FoR code in the Science and Engineering (SE) grouping. This is broadly comparable to the Canadian result, although they had slightly more in the Science and Engineering (SE) grouping and somewhat fewer in the Health Research (HR) grouping.

As noted in A.1, the response rate for the Australian survey was markedly lower than for the Canadian survey. This means that the results cannot necessarily be viewed as broadly representative of the Australian researcher population.

9.3 General Use of Cloud

More Australian respondents were users of cloud technologies (97.26%) than Canadian respondents (83.2%).

With respect to the cloud services used, the Australian and Canadian surveys both identified cloud storage as the main use case. The Canadian report states that “those researchers that did use cloud technologies mainly use them for storage solutions (SSH – 89%; SE – 78; HR – 84%), while researchers in Sciences and Engineering also use cloud for additional compute resources”. In fact, when considering the Canadian data the question was specifically about HPC (not just “additional compute resources”), and showed low usage for SSH (17%) ; highest usage by SE (61%); and with HR in between (46%). The Australian survey also found that SSH respondents were less likely to use HPC, whereas SE and HR usage was very similar.

Australian access to cloud services was (across all disciplines) preferentially by Secure Shell connection or software applications, with web browsers and remote connections third and fourth. The Canadian survey found that software applications were most popular, followed by web browsers, then Secure Shell. That survey also found a greater use of Secure Shell in the SE community, which was not visible in the Australian results.

In the Australian survey, respondents included in the SSH grouping were **less** likely to be influenced by ease of use or cost, and more likely than HR or SE to be influenced by other factors (such as institutional requirements or support).

9.4 Commercial Cloud

Use of commercial cloud was broadly comparable between the Canadian (close to 60%) and Australian (over 55%) respondents. Expenditure on commercial cloud by Canadian respondents from research grants was significantly higher (SSH – 56%; SE – 71%; HR – 72%) than for Australian respondents (SSH - 17.88%; SE - 38.89%; HR - 24.89%). Breaking down the responses for this question revealed a quarter of Canadian respondents (25.6%) accessed commercial cloud at no cost (23.53% for Australian respondents), with 30.77% of respondents spending less than \$1,000/year (20.59% for Australian respondents - significantly lower).

The Canadian survey found ease-of-use and access to flexible storage to be the main reasons why researchers turn to commercial cloud, whereas no particular reason dominated for the Australian respondents. Virtual machines on commercial cloud were used significantly less by Canadian respondents (SSH - 39%; SE - 54%; HR - 45%) than by Australian respondents, where this was the most used component (SSH - 56.52%; SE - 66.67%; HR - 70.59%). This may reflect a greater technical maturity in the Australian researchers, or a lack of alternatives. The difference in usage of shared file systems was also notable: Canadian (SSH - 64%; SE - 57%; HR - 52%) vs Australian (SSH - 43.48%; SE - 35.29%; HR - 55.88%).

9.5 Nectar Research Cloud/Alliance Community Cloud¹

Only 24% of Canadian respondents identified using the Alliance Community Cloud, compared to 63.77% for the Nectar Research Cloud. Access to additional computational resources was the main driver in both countries, although this was a much greater factor in Canada for SE respondents (83%) than for HR (61%) or SSH (55%). The equivalent results in Australia were SE - 25.49%, HR - 35.29%, and SSH - 17.39%.

When asked what elements or components of the Alliance Community Cloud researchers used specifically, virtual machines were by far the most used (SSH – 84%; SE – 83%; HR – 74%), with far fewer respondents reporting use of object storage or API access (SSH – 32% and 26%; SE – 23% and 26%; HR – 26% and 13% respectively). The equivalent data for the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud were similar in ranking, but not in quantity: virtual machines were by far the most used (SSH – 34.62%; SE – 43.86%; HR – 50%), with far fewer respondents reporting use of object storage or API access (SSH – 0% and 3.85%; SE – 0% and 3.51%; HR – 0% and 2.63% respectively). The survey misconfiguration for one question no doubt played a role here..

¹ The equivalent of the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud in Canada is the Alliance Community Cloud, and it is these numbers that have been used for comparison.

10. CONCLUSIONS

The use of cloud technologies is transforming all aspects of research, and the Australian research sector is not immune to this. The benefits it brings through scalable computing, ability to process massive datasets, and flexibility in resource allocation are significant. In addition, the use of cloud technologies supports facilitated collaboration with reduced friction and fewer barriers to entry. This is particularly valuable for interdisciplinary research projects that involve teams from diverse backgrounds drawn from a variety of sectors. Cloud usage can also act as an easier on-ramp to HPC usage where the research problem warrants this.

The ARDC Survey on Cloud Services Usage in Research has validated the importance of the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud in supporting the respondents' research by providing a range of computing capabilities. These include access to cloud resources through an eResearch platform such as Galaxy, EcoCommons or the Characterisation Virtual Laboratory. The two most common access paths were a direct terminal connection or a software layer, such as OneDrive or Jupyter Notebooks.

Over half of respondents said they used a commercial cloud provider, with the budget for this coming from a mix of institutional funds, research grants (these first two sources were the largest), as well as industry grants, personal funding and cloud research credits. No strong single factors were identified behind the use of commercial cloud. One danger that was identified in the use of commercial cloud was loss of data due to lack of continuity of funding - the percentage of respondents where this had occurred varied from 8.82% for HR researchers, 12% for SE, and 22.73% for SSH. This latter number is a cause for concern if the usage of commercial cloud increases and deserves further investigation.

Almost two thirds of respondents had used the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud. Access to additional computational resources, and the cost were each listed as reasons for use by around half of all respondents. When considering sharing sensitive/controlled data, twice as many respondents identified a need for this, as compared to those doing it. This suggests a possible unmet need in functionality or awareness.

Across respondents who used either commercial cloud or the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud, there was a clear need to be able to securely manage and share data with collaborators. While the survey did not ask about classes of collaborators, it seems likely that this would include industry collaborators, and that this need will grow over time.

When comparing use of commercial cloud vs the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud, an identified opportunity is to provide a wider range of cloud tools to assist with data transfer.

APPENDIX A: SURVEY DETAILS

A.1 Response rate

A total of 173 individuals responded to the survey. This is approximately half the response rate for the Canadian survey, scaled for population (the Canadian survey received 511 responses from a total population of 37.7M, which would scale to 345 responses for the Australian population of 25.5M). To increase the response rate, the survey deadline was extended from 16 June (at which point 152 responses had been received) to 23 June 2023.

A.2 Survey issues

One question was misconfigured in SurveyMonkey such that the survey text asked respondents to check multiple options if they applied, but the survey only accepted a single option response. This affected responses to Question 30 (What components of the Nectar Research Cloud do you use?). This was identified early on, but the staff member with edit access to the survey was on sick leave due to COVID, and so this could not be corrected in time.

Australian Research Data Commons

CONTACT

- ardc.edu.au
- +61 3 9902 0585
- contact@ardc.edu.au

FOLLOW

- [@ardc_au](https://twitter.com/ardc_au)
- [australian-research-data-commons](https://www.linkedin.com/company/australian-research-data-commons)
- [subscribe to our newsletter](#)

The ARDC
is enabled
by NCRIS